

EXPRESSION OF PROVERBS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGES AND THEIR SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7413965>

Humanity has created a rich spiritual treasure over the ages and left them as a cultural heritage from generation to generation. One of the foundations of our rich heritage is proverbs and sayings. Such masterpieces created by the people have been polished over the years and have taken a place in history.

Proverbs are created in our daily life, in people's interactions, and over time, they become a national treasure. It does not leave aside all aspects of life.

Proverbs increase a person's mind and mental activity and give direction in life.

In proverbs, work, love for the country, bravery, love, loyalty, friendship, honesty, truthfulness, feelings are glorified, dislike of work, lying, treachery, cowardice, etc. are condemned, evil. and fight against evil.

Both proverbs and proverbs are created in a unique folk art. In order for the proverbs to rise to the level of proverbs, they must boil in the cauldron of life, be recognized by the general public and become wisdom that is widely used.

The dictionary meaning of the word proverb also indicates this (proverb is an Arabic word that means "used" or "used" and serves for its effectiveness.

Any proverb is prepared and has a sign of completeness, and it is brought into the speech ready. It is different from other genres. The famous Russian lexicographer V. I. Dal distinguished between proverbs and proverbs and said: "A proverb is a flower, and a proverb is its fruit."

Proverbs are very close to proverbs. That is why they are always recorded together and published together.

A proverb is an admonition expressing a complete thought, expressed figuratively, usually based on phonetic rhythm and intonation.

Matal differs from proverb in that it does not contain a syntactically complete thought. The proverb is clear and fluent, and it reflects specific events and incidents. Therefore, they are kept in mind, passed from generation to generation, and their use has become a tradition.

In proverbs, they confirm the truth and have educational value, and are usually directed at the interlocutor.

It is known that the French, Uzbek and Russian languages are very different from each other in terms of lexical-grammatical aspects. In the languages of the nations of the world, you can find proverbs and sayings with the same or very close meaning. Such a rare product of thinking is common to the French, Uzbek and Russian languages.

For the French, Uzbek and Russian peoples, who differ from each other in their way of life, it is possible to get exactly the same alternative suitable proverbs only in terms of meaning.

Every nation has its favorite proverbs and sayings.

For example: the Russian nation "Beauty is the face,

And the word pleases the heart"

"Work glorifies a person

And laziness finds "

In Uzbeks, "Hungry stomach, quiet ear"

Proverbs such as "the sugar you have earned from your hard work and the honey from it" are used more often.

However, in many proverbs, the command form of the verb is used, and the meanings of ordering, begging, admonishing, and wishing are reflected.

For example: "Even if you find it on the ground, count it

"If you say goodbye, do it all."

The French proverb "Pas a pas on va loin" is translated into Uzbek "Movement-barakat", On ne touche pas deux lievres a la fois- "He who chases two rabbits cannot catch either" and the proverb "The water that catches two ships" it is equivalent to the proverb "he will drown". If the words in these sentences are translated literally, the intended meaning will not come out. Some proverbs have the content of informing, encouraging, explaining.

For example: "The old house has a fairy"

"A miser is not satisfied, a thief is not rich"

"Seven measures and one cut."

It is noted that the proverb "Mountain does not meet mountain" but man meets man is used in different languages. In some proverbs, the feelings of sweetness, kindness, hard work, friendship, kindness, loyalty are glorified, compared and expressed.

"Let your word be silver

Your work is golden."

Explanation: Rather than speaking well, do good deeds.

"Don't take off your boots without seeing water."

Note: Do not remove the bridge before reaching it.

"The next regret is your enemy."

Explanation: Believe in yourself rather than regret.

"If it doesn't hurt, stab someone else with a knife first."

Explanation: Do to others what you do to yourself.

"Happiness does not come from nowhere,

Make it with your own hands."

Explanation: Before one door closes, another opens.

"The blackness of your face is not a shame,

Shame on hypocrisy."

Explanation: A beautiful face can hide an ugly heart.

"One tried experiment is better than seven books."

Explanation: Experience is the mother of wisdom.

In conclusion, we can say that we should use proverbs correctly in our daily life. It is our priceless wealth that has been left to us from centuries to ages, from generation to generation. It will be appropriate if we apply them and use them to educate the young generation. Proverbs guide a person to the right path in life.

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